

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XXIII. Succinylation of β -Brazan

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It is shown that succinylation of β -brazan leads to substitution in the naphthalene nucleus and therefore benzoylation of β -brazan by Haworth's method should lead to an anthranocoumarone or a phenanthrocoumarone, of which the former is actually formed. This anthranocoumarone was previously prepared by *He et al.*¹ and was given the different structure. The compound along with its isomer has been prepared by *Bu Hoi et al.*² by the Elbs reaction. Their contention that the higher melting compound is naphtho-(2',3'-2,3)dibenzofuran is validated by the present work. The phenanthrocoumarone (VII) has now been unambiguously synthesised from coumarandione. In settling orientation problems, 9- and 2-ethyl- β -brazans have been unambiguously synthesised.

Very few experiments seem to have been carried out to effect rational synthesis of six theoretically possible dinaphthofurans although confusion exists in literature with regard to some of them. Moreover, methods of their preparation so far employed are not particularly universal so that unsymmetrically substituted dinaphthofurans can hardly be prepared by clear cut synthesis. The object of the present investigation is to devise unambiguous methods for the synthesis and the results are described in this and in the forthcoming communications.

An unambiguous synthesis of the linear dinaphthofuran (I) has already been described by Chatterjea *et al.*³ This compound was encountered previously by Curtis and *Vswanath*² as a byproduct during their preparation of 2,3,6,7-dibenzodiphenylene and also obtained by Clemo and Spence³ by oxidation of 2-naphthol in presence of catalysts, such as, alkaline earth oxides, although they did not identify the product. A different synthesis of (I) was envisaged by ring-fusion through succinylation. β -Brazan, on Friedel-

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 765.

2. *Ibid.*, 1959, 1670.

3. *Ibid.*, 1928, 2811.

Crafts' reaction with succinic anhydride, however, afforded the γ -keto-acid (II), the substitution having taken place in the naphthalene nucleus. The γ -keto-acid was reduced by the Wolff-Kishner method to γ -(9- β -brazan)butyric acid (III). This on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid furnished a single ketone, identified as (IV); this was reduced by lithium aluminium hydride to the related carbinol and then dehydrogenated by palladised charcoal to naphtho-(2',3'-2,3)dibenzofuran (V). The methyl derivative (VI) was prepared by the action of methylmagnesium iodide on the ketone (IV), followed by dehydrogenation. The structure of the ketone is based on the fact that if the alternative cyclisation of the acid afforded the angular ketone, then the final product (by reduction and dehydrogenation) should have been naphtho-(1',2'-2,3)dibenzofuran (VII). The latter was unambiguously synthesised, as shown below, from coumarandione which on condensation with 2-bromoacetylnaphthalene gave ethyl 2-(β -naphthoyl)-3-carboxylate (VIII). This was hydrolysed to the acid (IX) and then cyclised through the acid chloride to the quinone (X). The quinone on reduction with hydriodic acid furnished the phenanthrocoumarone (VII).

Borsche and Schake⁴ had earlier obtained an anthraquinone, formulated as (XII), by cyclisation of biphenylene-oxide-phthaloylic acid in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride. The acid was derived from dibenzofuran by the Friedel-Crafts reaction with phthalic anhydride in nitrobenzene. We have obtained the same compound by the action of phthalic anhydride on dibenzofuran with sodium aluminium chloride. As the reduction of this quinone by hydriodic acid or zinc dust distillation affords (V) (identity confirmed by mixed m.p. and UV spectrum), Borsche's earlier formulation of the quinone should be changed to (XI). Further, it may be mentioned that Buu-Hoi and Lavit⁵ obtained both (V) and (XIV) by the Elbs reaction on the ketone (XIII), cyclisation having taken place in the both possible positions. Their assumption that the higher melting isomer has the structure (V) is now validated by a direct comparison with authentic samples mentioned before.

4. *Ber.*, 1923, 56, 2498.

5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 38.

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We also tried the Elbs reaction on the ketone, 9-(*o*-toluoyl)- β -brazan (XV), obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of *o*-toluoyl chloride and β -brazan. Only one product was obtained in this case to which the structure (XVI) is assigned on the following grounds:

(XI)

(XII)

(XIII)

(XIV)

+ (V)

(XV)

(XVI)

(XVII)

- (i) The formation of angular structure is favoured in the Elbs reaction (cf. Bun-Hoi and Lavit⁵).
- (ii) The cyclisation at the 1-position of the naphthalene ring would be normally expected.
- (iii) If the compound had the alternative linear structure (XVII), it would be expected to absorb at higher wave lengths than the linear compound (V) because the λ_{max} is higher, the more elongated the molecule (Braude⁶). Actually both the compounds absorb approximately in the same range.

6. Braude, *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 42, 105.

The Friedel-Crafts acetylation of β -brazan, however, afforded a mixture of two products in which one of them was the major product; in this case also, apparently the substitution took place solely in the naphthalene nucleus. The acetyl derivatives were separated and reduced (Wolff-Kishner) to ethyl- β -brazans. One of these (major isomer) was identical with 9-ethyl- β -brazan (XXI) which was unambiguously synthesised in the following manner. Condensation of coumarandione with *p*-ethylphenacyl bromide (cf. Chatterjea⁷) in ethanolic sodium ethoxide afforded the *keto-ester* (XVIII). The related *acid* (XIX) was cyclised through the acid chloride to 9-ethyl- β -brazanquinone (XX) which was reduced by boiling with hydriodic acid to 9-ethyl- β -brazan.

The other ethyl- β -brazan was not identical with 2-ethyl- β -brazan (XXX) which would have been expected, had the acetylation taken place in the benzene nucleus. The scheme of the synthesis of the compound is shown below.

5-Ethylcoumarandione (XXVII), the starting material for the synthesis of 2-ethyl- β -brazaquinone, has been prepared as follows. *p*-Ethylphenol on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate afforded the *phenoxycetic ester* (XXII). The related acid (XXIII) cyclised in the presence of phosphoric anhydride and benzene to yield 5-ethylcoumaran-3-one (XXIV) which, on treatment with sodium nitrite and acetic acid afforded 2-isonitroso-5-ethylcoumaran-3-one (XXV). This was hydrolysed by concentrated hydrochloric acid to the α -keto-acid (XXVI) which cyclised easily in acetic anhydride to afford 5-ethylcoumarandione (XXVII). This dione condensed with phenacyl bromide as before to the acid (XXVIII) and thence to 2-ethyl- β -brazaquinone (XXX) through the brazaquinone (XXIX). From these results, it appears that the acetyl group in question is probably at the 6-position. We did not, however, carry out any experiment to establish this orientation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Friedel-Crafts Reaction of β -Brazaquinone with Succinic Anhydride.—A suspension of β -brazaquinone (2.1 g.) and succinic anhydride (1.2 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (15 ml.) and tetrachloroethane (15 ml.) was treated with aluminium chloride (3.0 g.) at 0°. The mixture gradually became brownish and β -brazaquinone slowly went into solution. The mixture was left in the refrigerator for 3 days and the solvents were removed in a current of steam. The residue was dissolved in potassium carbonate solution, filtered, and acidified. The resulting γ -ketoic acid (II) (1.5 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in darkish plates, m. p. 213°. On recrystallisation (with charcoal) a colorless material was obtained. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 4.5. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 75.5; H, 4.4%).

Wolff-Kishner Reduction.—The above acid (1.3 g.), dissolved in diethylene glycol (10 ml.), was treated with hydrazine hydrate (2 ml, 80%) and boiled for 1/2 hour. KOH (1.0 g.) was added, water removed from the system by distillation, and the temperature of the mixture raised to 200°. After 3 hours, the mixture was worked up to furnish the butyric acid (III) (0.7 g.), crystallising from benzene in colorless plates, m. p. 183-84°. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 5.0. $C_{20}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.9; H, 5.2%).

Cyclisation.—A suspension of the above acid (0.6 g.) in polyphosphoric acid (15.0 g.) was stirred at 170° for 1/2 hour. The mixture was cooled, treated with water, and the alkali-insoluble portion collected and filtered through an alumina column in benzene solution. On concentration of the benzene solution, the ketone (IV) (0.4 g.) was obtained in colorless plates, m. p. 247-48°. (Found: C, 84.6; H, 5.1. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 83.9; H, 4.9%).

From the mother liquor a further quantity of the ketone (0.5 g.) was recovered; there was no trace of isomeric material. The oxime crystallised from ethanol in thick plates, m. p. 255° (decomp.). (Found: C, 80.2; H, 5.2. $C_{20}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 79.7; H, 5.0%).

*All m. p. s. are uncorrected.

Naphtho-(2',3'-2,3)dibenzofuran (V).—On reduction of the above ketone (0.1 g.) in ethereal solution with excess of LiAlH_4 , the corresponding *carbinol* was obtained as a colorless crystalline mass which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal (0.05 g., 5%) yielded yellow plates of (V); it readily sublimed, m.p. $310-12^\circ$, unchanged on admixture with the material prepared by Borsche's method. The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid with a yellow colour, turning darkish green. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 237 μ (4.52), 268 μ . (4.87), 276 μ (4.88), 310 μ (4.40), 336 μ (3.89), 354 μ (3.74), 371 μ (3.94), and 396 μ (3.81) ($\log \epsilon$ in parenthesis).

The *trinitrofluorenone* derivative, prepared in benzene, crystallised from benzene as a dark crystalline mass, m.p. $230-34^\circ$. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 3.0. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_8\text{N}_3$ requires C, 67.9; H, 2.9%).

5'-Methylnaphtho-(2',3'-2,3)dibenzofuran (VI).—A solution of the ketone (IV) (0.1 g.) in dry ether (50 ml) was treated with an excess of MeMgI . On working up, the related *carbinol* was obtained as a crystalline mass which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal afforded the *anthracene* as yellow plates, m.p. $220-22^\circ$ from acetic acid. (Found: C, 89.1; H, 4.0. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 89.4; H, 4.9%).

2-(2-Naphthoyl)coumarone-3-carboxylic Acid (IX).—Coumarandione (1.5 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.25 g.) in dry methanol (15 ml). 2-Bromoacetylnaphthalene (2.5 g.) was added to the solution and the mixture refluxed for 3 hours. The mixture was treated with water, methanol removed by evaporation, and the oily residue was treated with excess of a 10% NaOH solution (50 ml). A sparingly soluble *sodium salt* separated. This was collected and acidified to provide the *acid* (IX) (1.2 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 178° (previous sintering). (Found: C, 76.4; H, 4.1. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 76.0; H, 3.8%).

Cyclisation.—The above acid (1.2 g.) was converted into acid chloride (by thionyl chloride), dissolved in CS_2 (15 ml), and treated in the cold with powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.0 g.). CS_2 was decanted after 12 hours and the dark complex on treatment with dilute acid afforded the *quinone* (X) (0.8 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in orange, fluffy needles, m.p. 226° . (Found: C, 80.7; H, 3.5. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 80.5; H, 3.3%).

On reductive acetylation, the corresponding *diacetate* was obtained, crystallising from acetic acid as a colorless, silky mass, m.p. $212-14^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 75.4; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 75.0; H, 4.2%).

Phenanthrocoumarone (X).—On boiling the quinone (0.1 g.) with freshly distilled HI (2.0 ml) for 18 hours, the *phenanthrocoumarone* (X) was isolated as colorless needles from ethanol, m.p. 136° . $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 228 μ (4.48), 249 μ (4.60), 260 μ (4.67), 268 μ (4.58), 293 μ (4.69), 305-306 μ (4.08), 319 μ (4.36), 334 μ (4.50), and 345 μ (3.71) ($\log \epsilon$ in parenthesis). (Found: C, 89.7; H, 4.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 89.5; H, 4.5%).

The *trinitrofluorenone* derivative, prepared in benzene, crystallised from benzene in silky needles, m.p. 282° . (Found: C, 67.6; H, 3.3. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_8\text{N}_3$ requires C, 67.9; H, 2.9%). The *picrate*, prepared in ethanol crystallised from ethanol in orange needles, m.p. $153-55^\circ$. (Found: C, 62.2; H, 3.1. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires C, 62.8; H, 3.0%).

9-o-Toluoyl- β -brazan (XV).— β -Brazan (2.1 g.) and *o*-toluoyl chloride (3.0 ml) were dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (20 ml) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 g.) was added to the solution gradually at 0°. The whole mass became dark red and after keeping it at room temperature for one day, it was warmed on a water bath (50°) for 6 hours. Next day, the mixture was decomposed with water and acidified with HCl. Nitrobenzene was removed by steam distillation when a dark brown gummy material was obtained which solidified. *2-o-Toluoyl- β -brazan* was purified over an alumina column, using benzene as a solvent. It was crystallised twice from ethyl acetate in colorless prisms, m.p. 217°. (Found: C, 86.2; H, 4.8. $C_{24}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 85.7; H, 4.7%).

Pyrolysis of (XV).—The mixture of the foregoing compound (0.5 g.) and zinc dust (0.05 g.) was heated over a metal bath (350-60°) for 4 hours. The product was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over an alumina column. The orange band, which was eluted first, was collected. On removal of the solvent, the compound (XVI) was isolated, crystallising from benzene in orange plates, m.p. >305°. λ_{max}^{KCl} 265-67 m μ (4.78), 300 m μ (4.33), 330-32 m μ (4.56), 398 m μ (4.23), and 424 m μ (4.13) (log ϵ in parenthesis). (Found: C, 90.45; H, 5.2. $C_{24}H_{14}O$ requires C, 90.50; H, 4.4%).

Acetylation of β -Brazan.—The mixture of β -brazan (2.18 g.) in moisture-free nitrobenzene (30 ml) and acetyl chloride (0.9 ml) was cooled in ice and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 g.) was gradually added to it with shaking when a light yellow complex separated. The mixture was left overnight and it was then warmed for 6 hours on a water bath (50°). After leaving it for one day more, it was decomposed with water and acidified with HCl. Nitrobenzene was removed in a current of steam when a dark brown lump was left. *9-Acetyl- β -brazan* was crystallised twice from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 154-55°. (Found: C, 82.6; H, 4.6. $C_{18}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 83.0; H, 4.6%).

Next day, a second crop was collected from the mother liquor, providing an impure material, m.p. 125-33°. A solution of this impure mixture in benzene was chromatographed over alumina column in presence of ultraviolet light. The non-fluorescent zone gave 6(?)*-acetyl- β -brazan* which crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid in colorless, prismatic needles, m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 83.4; H, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 83.0; H, 4.6%).

The blue fluorescent zone gave a compound which crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 156-57°, identical with the first fraction, mentioned above. The mixed m.p. of the two compounds showed depression.

Wolff-Kishner Reduction of the Acetyl Derivative.—The mixture of impure acetyl derivatives of β -brazan (crude mixture, 0.5 g.) in diethylene glycol (5 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml, 99-100%) was refluxed for 2 hours. On cooling, the crystalline hydrazones appeared. The mixture was then heated for 2 hours more at 200° with KOH (1.0 g.) after removing water from the system. The reaction product was diluted with water to provide a crystalline mixture which was purified over an alumina column using benzene as a solvent. *9-Ethyl- β -brazan* was eluted first, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 130-32°. (Found: C, 88.5; H, 5.8. $C_{18}H_{14}O$ requires C, 87.8; H, 5.7%). It showed no depression in mixed m.p. with the synthetic 9-ethyl- β -brazan, m.p. 134-35°.

It imparted a violet coloration to H_2SO_4 . The mother liquor on concentration gave a colorless compound (6-ethyl- β -brazan) which on recrystallisation from acetic acid melted at 110-11°. (Found: C, 87.6; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{14}O$ requires C, 87.8; H, 5.7%).

The Wolff-Kishner reduction of the pure acetyl derivative (m.p. 140-41°) gave the same compound which after purification by chromatography crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms; m.p. and mixed m.p. 110-11°. The Wolff-Kishner reduction of the 9-acetyl- β -brazan (m.p. 154-55°) gave 9-ethyl- β -brazan which crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 132-33°, alone or admixed with 9-ethyl- β -brazan.

2-p-Ethylbenzoylcoumarone-3-carboxylic Acid (XIX).—To a solution of sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.23 g.) in dry ethanol (15 ml) was added coumarandione (1.48 g.). Then *p*-ethyl- ω -bromoacetophenone⁶ (2.27 g.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hours. On cooling, the ester (XVIII) separated, which was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 80-81°, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 74.8; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 5.6%).

It dissolved in H_2SO_4 , forming a greenish yellow solution. The foregoing ester (1.5 g.) was hydrolysed by boiling it with aqueous ethanolic NaOH (3 ml, 30% and 20 ml ethanol) for 1/2 hour. After removing ethanol, the mixture afforded a crystalline sodium salt which was dissolved in water and acidified. The carboxylic acid (XVIII) crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colorless prisms, m.p. 121-22°, yield 0.55 g. (Found: C, 74.1; H, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8%).

9-Ethyl- β -brazanquinone (XX).—The above carboxylic acid (0.55 g.) was converted into acid chloride by refluxing it with thionyl chloride (2.0 ml) with a drop of pyridine for 45 minutes. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure and last traces of it removed by repeated addition of CS_2 , followed by its removal at reduced pressure. A solution of the acid chloride in dry CS_2 (15 ml) was cooled in ice and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 g.) was gradually added. A dark-coloured complex settled down. Next day, CS_2 was decanted, the complex decomposed in ice, and acidified. The quinone (XX) was washed successively with water, NH_4OH solution, and ethanol and crystallised from a large volume of ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 166-67°. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 4.4. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.3; H, 4.3%). The compound gave a violet coloration to H_2SO_4 (conc.).

Reduction of the Quinone (XX).—The foregoing quinone (0.3 g.) was boiled with HI (5 ml) for 4 hours. The mixture was poured over water and the colour of iodine was removed by addition of sodium bisulphite solution. 9-Ethyl- β -brazan (XXI) was filtered, washed with water, and purified over an alumina column, using benzene as a solvent. It crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m.p. 134-35°. The compound imparted a violet colour to H_2SO_4 (conc.).

p-Ethylphenoxyacetic Acid (XXIII).—A mixture of *p*-ethylphenol (9.0 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (9.0 ml), and potassium carbonate (20 g.) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed for 6 to 7 hours. On working up, ethyl *p*-ethylphenoxyacetate (XXII) was obtained as a colorless oil, b.p. 188-90°/70 mm, yield 10 g. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 7.0. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%).

Hydrolysis.—The foregoing ester (5.0 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing it with aqueous ethanolic NaOH (40 ml, 10% and 10 ml ethanol) for 1/2 hour. After removing ethanol, a colorless crystalline sodium salt separated. On acidification, a colorless oil was obtained

which solidified on cooling in ice. *p*-Ethylphenoxyacetic acid crystallised from water in colorless plates, m.p. 92-94° (Ipatieff *et al.*⁹ reported m.p. 96°); yield 4.0 g.

5-Ethylcoumaran-3-one (XXIV).—A solution of the foregoing acid (4.0 g.) in benzene (80 ml) was treated with P₂O₅ (20.7 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours. On working up as usual, a liquid was obtained which on steam distillation afforded a colorless oil, identified as 5-ethylcoumaran-3-one. It gave a *semicarbazone*, crystallising from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 233-34°. (Found: N, 19.57. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N₃ requires N, 19.20%).

5-Ethylcoumarandione (XXVII).—To a solution of the foregoing coumaranone (6.0 g.) in glacial acetic acid (60 ml) sodium nitrite (12.0 g.) was added in four instalments at the interval of 1 hour. Next day, the mixture was diluted with water and *isonitroso compound* (XXV) was collected and crystallised from acetic acid or benzene in pale yellow needles, m.p. 156-57°, yield 3.0 g. (Found: C, 57.4; H, 5.4. C₁₁H₉O₃N₂H₂O requires C, 57.4; H, 5.2%).

This *isonitroso compound* (5.0 g.) was heated on a water bath for 1½ hour with HCl (conc., 20 ml). An oily liquid separated which on cooling gave a crystalline α -*keto-acid* (XXVI), m.p. 70-80° (crude sample), yield 4.0 g. It was very soluble in water and its crystallisation was uneconomical. This α -*keto-acid* was cyclised by heating with acetic anhydride (10 ml) for 5 minutes on a water bath. The excess of acetic anhydride was removed at reduced pressure and 5-ethylcoumarandione distilled (b.p. 155°, 2 mm) as an oil which solidified quickly; m.p. 65°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 4.5. C₁₀H₈O₂ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.5%).

It gave a yellow crystalline *quinoxaline derivative* on condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine in acetic acid, m.p. 262°. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 5.4. C₁₆H₁₄O₂N₂ requires C, 72.1; H, 5.2%).

2-Benzoyl-5-ethylcoumarone-3-carboxylic Acid (XXVIII).—5-Ethylcoumarandione (2.0 g.) was added in a solution of sodium ethoxide (from 0.3 g. of sodium) in dry ethanol (20 ml). The solution became red, turning slowly to dark green. When phenacyl bromide (2.3 g.) was added, the colour became brown. The solution was refluxed over a steam bath for 2 hours when sodium bromide separated within 15 minutes. After cooling, water (5 ml) was added and the resulting dark oil solidified on cooling. Ethyl 2-benzoylcoumarone-3-carboxylate crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 148-50°, yield 2.2 g. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 5.8. C₂₀H₁₈O₄ requires C, 74.6; H, 5.6%).

The foregoing ester (2.2 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (15 ml) containing NaOH (5 ml, 30%) and the solution was refluxed for 45 minutes. After removing ethanol from the reaction mixture, the *sodium salt* separated which was dissolved in hot water and acidified with HCl. The *carboxylic acid* (XXVIII) crystallised from benzene in pale yellow needles, m.p. 168-70°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 73.4; H, 4.9. C₁₈H₁₆O₄ requires C, 73.4; H, 4.8%).

2-Ethyl- β -brazanquinone (XXIX).—A solution of the foregoing acid (0.7g.) in thionyl chloride (3.0 ml) was treated with a drop of pyridine and refluxed for 45 minutes in an oil bath at 100°. The excess of thionyl chloride was removed at reduced pressure. To the

solution of the acid chloride in dry CS_2 (20 ml) anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.0 g.) was added with constant shaking at 0° . A dark-coloured complex was formed. Next day, CS_2 was decanted and aluminium chloride complex was decomposed with iced HCl . 2-Ethyl- β -brazanquinone was filtered, washed with water, NH_4OH solution, and finally with ethanol. It crystallised from acetic acid (charcoal) as a yellow powder, m.p. $195-96^\circ$, yield 0.35 g. (Found: C, 78.0; H, 4.5. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 78.2; H, 4.4%). It gave a violet coloration to H_2SO_4 (conc.).

2-Ethyl- β -brazan (XXX).—The foregoing quinone (0.25 g.) was boiled with freshly distilled HI (10 ml) for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was diluted with water and the colour of iodine was discharged by adding sodium bisulphite solution. 2-Ethyl- β -brazan was filtered and purified over an alumina column, using benzene as a solvent. It crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid in colorless shining plates, m.p. $103-104^\circ$. (Found: C, 87.6; H, 5.8. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 88.0; H, 5.7%).

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